

EATING DISORDERS AND ITS AFFECTS TO ORGANISM.

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Abstract: Eating disorders are mental illnesses characterized by severe disturbances in eating behaviors, body image, and thoughts about food.

Introduction: Eating disorders are psych-neurological illnesses that damage a person's physical and mental health and diminish their overall quality of life, affecting relationships, work, and personal development. The condition occurs due to different factors, like biological (genetics), physiological (mental health disorders), environmental and dieting. Symptoms vary, depending on the type of eating disorder. The most common types of eating disorders are anorexia and bulimia.

The purpose of the study. Eating disorders are serious conditions related to persistent eating behaviors that negatively affect your health, your emotions and your ability to function in important areas of life. The most common eating disorders are anorexia nervosa, bulimia nervosa and binge-eating disorder. People with eating disorders can have all different body types and sizes. Also there is no an age limit, both adults and young people can have eating disorders.

Methods and techniques. Anorexia also called anorexia nervosa is an eating disorder in which a person tries to achieve the lowest possible body weight. Despite having dangerously low body weight, a person feels fat and is afraid of gaining weight. People with anorexia often use extreme efforts to control weight and shape, which often seriously interfere with health and daily life. Methods used by patients with anorexia are: limiting calories or cutting out certain kinds of foods or food groups, exercising too much, using laxatives or diet aids, or vomiting after eating. There is a range of signs and symptoms of anorexia; these include: sleep disturbances, dry skin, hair loss, lack of circulation in hands and feet and extreme fear of gaining weight. Bulimia nervosa is an eating disorder characterized by recurrent episodes of binge eating, excessive concern about body weight, and extreme measures to control it. Typical symptoms of bulimia are: the person does not stop eating even he feels full, the individual constantly seeks ways to prevent weight gain, digestive problems begin, salivation increases, throat inflammations become more frequent, dermatitis appears, moral and physical strength weakens. When diagnosed with bulimia, treatment is conducted in several directions: medication therapy, psychotherapy, dietary therapy, vitamin therapy.

Results. The primary focus of treatment is to eliminate the causes of bulimia and free the patient from the negative emotions that trigger overeating. The psychiatrist teaches the patient to perceive their body correctly, including through the use of cognitive-behavioral therapy. In cases of neurotic and depressive disorders, the patient may be prescribed sedatives, neurotropic medications, and antidepressants.

Conclusion. Eating disorders, including anorexia nervosa and bulimia nervosa, are serious psychoneurological illnesses that profoundly impact both physical and mental health. The complex interplay of different factors contributes to the development of these disorders, leading to severe symptoms that require comprehensive treatment approaches. Ultimately,

understanding the multifaceted nature of eating disorders and providing timely, multidisciplinary treatment can significantly improve the chances of recovery and help individuals regain control over their lives, fostering better physical health and emotional well-being.

Used literature

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